

4th International Summer School on Non-Target Metabolomics Data Mining for Exposomics and Natural Products Research

Technical University of Denmark, 18th - 22th August 2025

Monday, August 18th 2025, Introduction

8.00-9.00	Registration, Breakfast and Coffee	
9.00-9.30	Welcome and introduction	Lone Gram, Scott Jarmusch and Martin Hansen, Technical University of Denmark
9.30-10.15	Mass spectrometry basics in metabolomics I	Corinna Brungs, University of Vienna, Austria Daniel Petras, University of California
10.15-10.30	Break	
10.30-11.15	Mass spectrometry basics in metabolomics II	Corinna Brungs, University of Vienna, Austria Daniel Petras, University of California
11.15-11.30	Break	
11.30-12.15	Study design, quality assurance, quality control and best practices	Martin Hansen, Technical University of Denmark
12.15-13.15	Lunch break	
13.15-14.00	Data management: security, FAIR principles and data repositories	Justin van der Hooft, Wageningen University & Research Madeleine Ernst, Statens Serum Institut
14.00-14.15	Introduction to hands on exercise, groups and the datasets	Scott Jarmusch and Martin Hansen, Technical University of Denmark
14.15-14.45	Break	
14.45-15.30	General introduction MS data conversion, data structures, data exploration	Steffen Heuckeroth and Robin Schmid, mzio GmbH Corinna Brungs, University of Vienna
15.30-15.45	Break	
15.45-16.45	Working on data in groups: Raw data assessment in mzmine	
16.45-17.00	mzmine Q&A	Steffen Heuckeroth and Robin Schmid, mzio GmbH Corinna Brungs, University of Vienna
17.00-19.00	Social event: Ice breaker	

Tuesday, August 19th 2025, Data preprocessing

8.00-9.00	Breakfast	
9.00-9.45	Data preprocessing in mzmine I: Introduction to data processing	Steffen Heuckeroth and Robin Schmid, mzio GmbH Corinna Brungs, University of Vienna
9.45-10.00	Break	
10.00-10.45	Data preprocessing in mzmine II: Optimization of feature detection	Steffen Heuckeroth and Robin Schmid, mzio GmbH Corinna Brungs, University of Vienna
10.45-11.00	Break	
11.00-12.00	Working on data in groups	
12.00-12.30	Metabolite annotation: Introduction to mzmine annotation and molecular networking	Steffen Heuckeroth and Robin Schmid, mzio GmbH Corinna Brungs, University of Vienna
12.30-13.30	Lunch break	
13.30-14.15	Data preprocessing in mzmine III: Compound annotation and export	Steffen Heuckeroth and Robin Schmid, mzio GmbH Corinna Brungs, University of Vienna
14.15-15.00	Working on data in groups	
15.00-15.30	Break	
15.30-16.10	mzmine: Live demo and library generation	Steffen Heuckeroth and Robin Schmid, mzio GmbH Corinna Brungs, University of Vienna
16.10-16.15	Instructions for SIRIUS work Wednesday	Markus Fleischauer and Jonas Emmert, Friedrich-Schiller University Jena
16.15-17.00	Keynote: Non-target chemical analysis of drinking water and exposure assessment	Mulatu Y Nanusha, Technical University of Denmark
	Social event	

Wednesday, August 20th 2025, Metabolite annotation

8.00-9.00	Breakfast	
9.00-9.30	Introduction to metabolite identification	Scott Jarmusch, Technical University of Denmark Daniel Petras, University of California Allegra Aron, University of Denver
9.30-10.30	Global natural product social molecular networking (GNPS2)	Scott Jarmusch, Technical University of Denmark Daniel Petras, University of California Allegra Aron, University of Denver
10.30-11.00	Break	
11.00-12.30	Turning tandem mass spectra into metabolite structures (SIRIUS)	Markus Fleischauer and Jonas Emmert, Friedrich-Schiller University Jena
12.30-13.30	Lunch break	
13.30-14.00	Network analysis with Cytoscape	Allegra Aron, University of Denver Daniel Petras, University of California
14.00-14.30	Integrating SIRIUS into GNPS2 and Cytoscape network analysis	Scott Jarmusch, Technical University of Denmark Daniel Petras, University of California
14.30-16.00	Working on data in groups	
16.00-16.30	Break	
16.30-17.30	Keynote: Advanced metabolite annotation tools and newest developments within GNPS2	Mingxun Wang, University of California
	Social event	

Thursday, August 21st 2025, Substructure discovery and advanced metabolite annotation

8.00-9.00	Breakfast	
9.00-10.15	Introduction to Jupyter notebooks and Python	Florian Huber, Düsseldorf University of Applied Sciences Saer Samanipour, University of Amsterdam
10.15-11.00	Processing and similarity evaluation of mass spectrometry data (Matchms)	Florian Huber and Julian Pollmann, Düsseldorf University of Applied Sciences
11.00-11.30	Break	
11.30-12.30	Advanced metabolite annotation with MS2Query and MS2LDA	Florian Huber and Julian Pollmann, Düsseldorf University of Applied Sciences Justin van der Hooft, Wageningen University & Research
12.30-13.30	Lunch break	
13.30-14.00	<i>Keynote:</i> Molecular space evaluation	Saer Samanipour, University of Amsterdam
14.00-15.00	Metabolomic data analysis with FERMO	Justin van der Hooft, Wageningen University & Research
15.00-15.30	Break	
15.30-17.00	Working on data in groups	
	Social event	

Friday, August 22nd 2025, Statistical analysis and data visualization

8.00-9.00	Breakfast	
9.00-10.00	Multivariate and univariate statistical analyses	Madeleine Ernst, Statens Serum Institut Filip Ottosson, Aalborg University Saer Samanipour, University of Amsterdam
10.00-10.30	Hitchhiker's Stats Guide and Web application	Abzer K. Pakkir Shah, University of Tübingen
10.30-11.00	Break	
11.00-12.30	Working on data in groups	
12.30-13.30	Lunch break	
13.30-14.00	Keynote: Untargeted Metabolomics Reveals Novel Metal-Binding Molecules	Allegra Aron, University of Denver
14.00-14.30	Working on data in groups	
14.30-15.00	Break	
15.00-16.45	Project presentations in groups (four parallel sessions)	
16.45-17.00	Conclusion of the Summer school and farewell drinks	